

SEARCH FOR NEW ANTIMALARIALS. PART V. SYNTHESIS OF SOME 8-AMINOALKYLAMINO- AND 8-DIALKYLAMINOALKYLAMINO-CHROMONES

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Twentyfive 8-aminoalkylamino- and 8 dialkylaminoalkylamino-chromones have been synthesised as possible antimalarials.

In view of the antimalarials chloroquine and camoquine having proved to be effective amoebacidal agents (Conan, *Amer. J. Trop. Med.*, 1948, 28, 107; Hoekenga *et al*, *ibid.*, 1950, 30, 625), it was thought worthwhile to synthesise some compounds as antimalarials, based on the structure of certain potential amoebacides. Considering the high amoebacidal activity exhibited by the Mannich bases derived from substituted chromanones (2:3-dihydrochromones) (Wiley, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4205), aminoalkylamino and dialkylaminoalkylamino side chains have been introduced in substituted chromones for studying their antimalarial activity.

In the present investigation, the required 7-substituted chromones were obtained by reacting ethyl formate with various 4-substituted-2-hydroxyacetophenones in ether in the cold, following the method of Späth and Lederer (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 743), modified by Joshi *et al.* (this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 59). The 7-methoxychromone was also demethylated with anhydrous aluminium chloride to 7-hydroxychromone. These chromones, on nitration at 0° , yielded the 8-nitrochromones (Joshi *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) which, on reduction with iron powder and water in the presence of ferrous sulphate (Hodgson and Marsden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 398), yielded the corresponding 8-aminochromones.

The 8-aminoalkylamino- and 8-dialkylaminoalkylamino-chromones were prepared by refluxing the 8-aminochromones with various amino- and dialkylamino-alkyl bromide-hydrobromides in dry benzene in the presence of an excess of anhydrous potassium carbonate and were isolated as dihydrochlorides in the usual way. The antimalarial activities of the compounds are under investigation at the Malaria Institute of India, Delhi.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

4-Substituted 2-Hydroxyacetophenones.—Resacetophenone (Robinson and Shah, *ibid.*, 1934, 1491) was methylated to paeanol (4-methoxy-2-hydroxyacetophenone) (Crabtree and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1918, 113, 868). 4-Ethoxy-2-hydroxyacetophenone was obtained in the same way by ethylation with ethyl iodide and KOH in methanol. 4-Methyl- and 4-ethyl-2-hydroxyacetophenones were prepared by the Fries rearrangement of *m*-cresyl acetate (Rosenmund and Schnurr, *Annalen*, 1928, 460, 56) and *m*-ethyl phenylacetate (Sen and Tiwari, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 357) respectively.

7-Substituted chromones were prepared by following the method described by Joshi *et al.* (*loc.cit.*). To a suspension of powdered sodium (0.3M) in dry ether (50 c.c.) a cold solution of the substituted *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (0.1M) in dry and freshly distilled ethyl formate (25 c.c.) was added in small lots with shaking. The reaction mixture was left for 4 hours in an ice-chest and then overnight at room temperature, after which the ethyl formate-ether mixture (1:10, 40 c.c.) was added and the whole refluxed for 1 hour on a water-bath. After cooling, water (100 c.c.) was added and the alkaline aqueous layer separated. It was strongly acidified with 50% H₂SO₄ and heated on a water-bath for 1 hour. On cooling and subsequent neutralisation with solid sodium bicarbonate, the chromone separated out as a solid, which was filtered, washed with 5% aqueous sodium carbonate and then with water, and finally recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°).

The 7-methoxychromone was also demethylated to 7-hydroxychromone with anhydrous aluminium chloride. A solution of 7-methoxychromone (0.023M) in CS₂ was slowly added with stirring to a filtered solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.048M) in CS₂. The crystalline addition product was filtered and dried in vacuum. It was refluxed in benzene solution for 3 hours. The semisolid mass obtained on cooling was separated from benzene and poured in water (15 c.c.). The 7-hydroxychromone separating was purified by dissolving it in hot benzene and reprecipitating with petroleum ether. The m.p., yield, etc. of these chromones are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

R.	C h r o m o n e s.					O x i m e s.				
	M.P.	Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.		Found.	Calc.	
OH	...	...	...	...	...	...	283°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₃ N	7.87	7.91
OMe	...	...	...	...	...	...	154°	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N	7.29	7.25
OEt	103°	49%	69.36	69.47	5.29	5.26	131-32°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	6.77	6.83
Me	66°	43	74.88	75.00	4.90	5.00	112°	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N	7.91	8.00
Rt	53-54°	46	75.79	75.86	5.81	5.75	98-99°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	7.38	7.41

7-Substituted 8-Nitrochromones.—Nitration of 7-substituted chromones resulted in the formation of the corresponding 8-nitrochromone (Joshi *et al.*, *loc.cit.*). A mixture of H_2SO_4 (d 1.8, 4.2 c.c.) and HNO_3 (d 1.42, 1.4 c.c.) was slowly added with continuous stirring to a solution of the 7-substituted chromone (0.02M) in H_2SO_4 (d 1.8, 17.5 c.c.). The mixture was kept at 0° for 4 hours and then poured over crushed ice (100 g.). The nitrochromone separated as a yellow solid which was filtered and recrystallised from ethyl acetate or ethanol. These nitrochromones are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Nitrochromones.					Oximes.			
R.	M.P.	Yield.	% Nitrogen.		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
OH	...	...	...	...	291°	$C_9H_5O_3N_2$	12.48	12.61
OMe	...	...	...	...	267°	$C_{10}H_7O_3N_2$	11.85	11.86
OEt	219°	93%	5.87	5.96	271-72°	$C_{11}H_{10}O_3N_2$	11.26	11.20
Me	181°	96	6.81	6.83	204°	$C_{10}H_9O_3N_2$	12.77	12.73
Et	163°	88	6.28	6.39	211-13°	$C_{11}H_{10}O_3N_2$	11.93	11.97

Oximes of the various chromones and nitrochromones, prepared in the usual way, are recorded in Table I and Table II respectively.

7-Substituted 8-aminochromones were obtained by the reduction of the above nitrochromones with iron powder and water in presence of ferrous sulphate (Hodgson and Marsden, *loc.cit.*). A mixture of the substituted 8-nitrochromone (0.02M), iron powder (10 g.) and ferrous sulphate (1 g.) was refluxed in water (100 c.c.) for 1 hour; ammonia (d 0.88, 1 c.c.) was added to precipitate iron and the solution was filtered. The aminochromone separated as fine needles on passing CO_2 in the filtrate and subsequent concentration and cooling.

The aminochromones and their oximes and *N*-acetyl derivatives, prepared in the usual way, are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

R.	Amino chromones		Oximes		N-Acetyl derivatives.					
	M.P.	Yield.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.				
OH	199°	41	8.39%	8.38	13.99	14.06	M.P.	Formula. <td>% Nitrogen.</td>	% Nitrogen.	
OMe	167°	53	7.30	7.33	13.51	13.59	257-58°	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₄ N	6.36	6.39
OEt	161-62°	38	6.77	6.83	12.68	12.73	233°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	6.12	6.01
Me	130-31°	47	7.89	8.00	14.70	14.74	245°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	5.65	5.67
Et	117-19°	40	7.33	7.41	13.69	13.73	178-79°	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	6.39	6.45
							159-60	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	6.05	6.06

Chromone dihydrochlorides.				O x i m e s.				D i p i c r a t e s.				
No.	M.P.	Yield.	% Nitrogen.		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	Found.	Calc.
			Found.	Calc.								
R' = H; n=1.												
OH.	280°	61%	9.51	9.56	168-69°	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₃	17.84	17.87	202°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₁₇ N ₆	16.47	16.52
OMe	297-98°	76	8.98	9.12	157-58°	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₃	16.89	16.86	178-79°	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₁₇ N ₆	17.71	17.72
OEt	276-77°	70	8.70	8.72	153°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃	16.03	15.96	181°	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₁₇ N ₆	15.81	15.86
Me	201°	69	9.67	9.62	141°	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃	17.99	18.02	160-61°	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₁₆ N ₆	16.48	16.57
Et	189-90°	57	9.18	9.15	132-33°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃	16.87	17.00	152-53	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₁₆ N ₆	16.20	16.23
R' = Et; n=1.												
OH	251-52°	52	7.97	8.02	156-57°	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	14.42	14.43	177°	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ O ₁₇ N ₆	16.18	16.26
OMe	273-74°	61	7.68	7.71	154°	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	13.59	13.77	165-66°	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₁₇ N ₆	14.99	14.97
OEt	243°	65	7.37	7.43	147-48°	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃	13.06	13.17	141-42°	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₁₇ N ₆	14.53	14.70
Me	221-22°	64	8.02	8.07	122-23°	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃	14.58	14.53	128°	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₁₆ N ₆	15.25	15.30
Et	167-68°	70	7.70	7.76	109-11°	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃	13.79	13.86	137°	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₁₆ N ₆	14.88	15.01
R' = Pr; n=1.												
OH	249-50°	57	7.44	7.43	147-48°	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃	13.14	13.17	157°	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₁₇ N ₆	14.62	14.70
OMe	263°	64	7.06	7.16	131-32°	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₃	12.57	12.61	138-39°	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₇ N ₆	14.37	14.43
OEt	267°	53	6.88	6.91	141-42°	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₃	12.03	12.10	161-62°	C ₃₁ H ₂₈ O ₁₇ N ₆	14.07	14.18
Me	209°	49	7.43	7.47	117°	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃	13.22	13.25	153°	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₆ N ₆	14.71	14.74
Et	199-200°	51	7.15	7.20	103-104°	C ₁₉ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₃	12.67	12.69	129-30°	C ₃₁ H ₂₈ O ₁₆ N ₆	14.45	14.47
R' = Et; n=3.												
OH	224-25°	40	7.33	7.43	119-20°	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃	13.09	13.17	156-57°	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₁₇ N ₆	14.71	14.70
OMe	209-10°	58	7.11	7.16	100-101°	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₃	12.55	12.61	137°	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₇ N ₆	14.40	14.43
OEt	177°	60	6.88	6.91	109°	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₃	12.18	12.10	122-23°	C ₃₁ H ₂₈ O ₁₇ N ₆	14.03	14.18
Me	146°	45	7.46	7.47	89-90°	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃	13.17	13.25	126°	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₆ N ₆	14.79	14.74
Et	131-32°	52	7.19	7.20	78°	C ₁₉ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₃	12.65	12.69	128-29°	C ₃₁ H ₂₈ O ₁₆ N ₆	14.42	14.47
R' = Pr; n=3.												
OH	227°	59	6.98	6.91	101-103°	C ₁₉ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₃	11.96	12.10	144°	C ₃₁ H ₂₈ O ₁₇ N ₆	14.20	14.18
OMe	202-204°	60	6.67	6.68	76°	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₃	11.60	11.63	127-28°	C ₃₂ H ₃₀ O ₁₇ N ₆	13.88	13.93
OEt	122-23°	53	6.44	6.47	81-82°	C ₂₁ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₃	11.12	11.20	136-37°	C ₃₃ H ₃₂ O ₁₇ N ₆	13.39	13.41
Me	118-19°	46	6.92	6.95	63°	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₃	11.99	12.17	128°	C ₃₂ H ₃₀ O ₁₆ N ₆	14.17	14.21
Et	109-11°	48	6.68	6.72	46°	C ₂₁ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₃	11.63	11.70	131°	C ₃₃ H ₃₂ O ₁₆ N ₆	13.84	13.96

δ -Dipropylⁿaminobutyl bromide-hydrobromide was prepared by distilling δ -dipropylⁿaminobutanol with 48% hydrobromic acid, following the method of Cortese (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 191), m.p. 93°, yield 53%. (Found: N, 4.47; Br, 50.41. $C_{10}H_{23}NBr_2$ requires N, 4.42; Br, 50.47%).

δ -Dipropylⁿaminobutanol required for the above reaction was prepared from tetramethylenechlorohydrin (Kirner and Richter, *ibid.*, 1929, **51**, 2503) (0.1M) and dipropylⁿ-amine (0.13M) by a similar procedure as described by Burnett *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1937, **59**, 2248); b.p. 66-69°/12 mm, yield 61%. (Found: N, 7.93. $C_{10}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 8.09%).

δ -Diethylaminobutyl bromide-hydrobromide was similarly obtained from tetramethylenechlorohydrin and diethylamine, m.p. 117°, yield 67%. (Found: N, 4.81; Br, 55.27. $C_8H_{19}NBr_2$ requires N, 4.84; Br, 55.36%).

β -Dipropylⁿaminoethyl bromide-hydrobromide, β -diethylaminoethyl bromide-hydrobromide and β -aminoethyl bromide-hydrobromide were prepared in the same way by the known methods (Amundsen and Krantz, *ibid.*, 1941, **63**, 305; Cortese, *loc. cit.*)

δ -Aminoalkylamino- and δ -dialkylaminoalkylamino-chromones were obtained by refluxing the δ -aminochromones (0.05M) with various amino- and dialkylamino alkyl bromide-hydrobromides (0.05M) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.11M) in dry benzene for 5 hours, removing the solvent and extracting the residue with ether. Base dihydrochlorides were prepared by passing HCl gas into the dried ether extract and then recrystallised from 75% ethanol.

The oximes and the dipicrates of the bases were prepared by the usual procedures. The m.p., yield, analysis, etc. of the dihydrochlorides, oximes and dipicrates of the bases are recorded in Table IV.